

Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Refactorings for systems implemented in the Elixir functional language

Institution: DCC / ICEx / UFMG

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand the main refactoring strategies used in code implemented in the Elixir functional language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception about the refactoring strategies in Elixir (use frequency and impact on system quality)

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 20 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br.

If you have questions about the ethical aspects of this research: Contact the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (COEP-UFMG). Address: Av. Antônio Carlos, 6627. Administrative Unit II – 2nd floor - Room 2005. Pampulha Campus. Belo Horizonte – MG, Brazil. CEP: 31270-901. E-mail: coep@prpq.ufmg.br. Phone: +55 (31) 3409-4592. Opening hours: 09:00 AM to 11:00 AM; 02:00 PM to 04:00 PM (UTC-3).

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Próxima

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

Select your country: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

Your city: *

Sua resposta

Voltar

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

Perceptions on the Relevance and Prevalence of refactorings

Refactoring strategies are **code transformations that do not alter a program's behavior**. In our research, we aim to catalog and document refactorings for the Elixir programming language. We would like to know your perception regarding these refactorings.

Therefore, based on your experience, answer the questions below.

[Prevalence] How often do you perform this refactoring in your Elixir systems or see this refactoring being carried out in code implemented with this language?
(1 = it is very rare; 5 = it is very common)

[Relevance] How relevant is this refactoring in Elixir systems? (i.e., when answering consider the potential of this refactoring to have a positive impact on maintainability, comprehensibility, and evolution of Elixir code)
(1 = very low impact and relevance; 5 = high impact and relevance)

Notes:

- Each refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link containing code examples;
- You don't have to answer all questions items if you don't want to.

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Generalise a process abstraction]**.

This refactoring aims to transform *Task* or *Agent* process abstractions into *GenServer* when the first ones are used beyond their suggested purposes. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Converts guards to conditionals]**.

This refactoring aims to replace all guards in a multi-clause function with traditional conditionals, creating only one clause for the function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Folding against a function definition]**.

This refactoring can remove duplicated code, replacing a set of expressions with a call to an existing function that performs the same processing as the duplicated code. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Moving "with" clauses without pattern matching]**.

In Elixir, it is possible to define a "with" statement using an initial or final clause without pattern matching. This refactoring can be used to: (1) move outside, placing just before the "with" statement, an initial clause that doesn't match anything; or (2) move into the body of a "with" statement a final clause that doesn't match anything. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[List comprehension simplifications]**.

This refactoring aims to transform a list comprehension (i.e., *for* construct) into semantically equivalent calls to the functions *Enum.map/2* or *Enum.filter/2*. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Remove dead code]**.

This refactoring aims to clean the codebase by eliminating code definitions that are not being used. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Behaviour inlining]**.

In Elixir, a *behaviour* is an interface that a module (i.e., *behaviour instance*) can implement to define functions in a guided way. This refactoring aims to eliminate the implementations of callbacks in a *behaviour instance*, moving the function that implements callbacks to the *behaviour definition* module. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Widen or narrow definition scope]**.

This refactoring aims to widen the scope of a nested anonymous function within a named function, by transforming it into a separate named function. The reverse operation can also be performed to narrow a function's usage scope. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Remove unnecessary calls to length/1]**.

This refactoring aims to replace unnecessary calls to *length/1* in guard clauses with pattern matching. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Add or remove a parameter]**.

This refactoring is used when it is necessary to request additional information from the callers of a function or the opposite situation when some information passed by the callers is no longer necessary. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Merging multiple definitions]**.

This refactoring (a.k.a. *tupleing*) aims to group complementary functions, that have identical code snippets, into a single function that returns a *tuple*. Each original return provided by the merged functions will be contained in different elements of the *tuple* returned by the new function. This transformation avoids multiple traversals over a data structure. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Static structure reuse]**.

This refactoring aims to eliminate unnecessary recreations of identical structure structures (e.g., *lists* or *tuples*) by assigning them to variables that allow these structures to be shared throughout the code. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Replace "Enum" collections with "Stream"]**.

This refactoring aims to replace the use of the *Enum* module with the *Stream* module when multiple operations in large collections are performed together (i.e., in a pipeline). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Remove nested conditional statements and function calls]**.

This refactoring aims to replace nested conditional statements (e.g., "case"), used as a parameter of a function call, with strict equality comparisons (i.e., *==*). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Moving a definition]**.

This refactoring moves a definition (e.g., *function*, *macro*, or *struct*) between modules when it accesses more definitions from another module other than its own or is used more frequently by another module. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the **prevalence** and **relevance** level of the refactoring **[Splitting a definition]**.

This refactoring aims to separate a recursive function by creating distinct recursive functions, each responsible for individually generating a respective element originally contained in a tuple. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Voltar

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Final remarks

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

Yes

No

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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